

Integrative Medicine for Acne Vulgaris: The Role of Naturopathy, Diet modification, Ozone therapy, home remedies, yoga therapy, Meditation and Stress Reduction

Dr. M.V.P. Thirumuruga Thilagavathi,
BNYS, Sivaraj Naturopathy
and Yoga Medical College, Salem, Tamil Nadu.

Dr. K. Satya Lakshmi,
Director of National Institute of
Naturopathy, Pune.

Dr Reshma Jogdand,
BNYS, MSc, (PhD Scholar), Assistant
Professor, Department of Yoga, National Institute of Naturopathy,
Pune.

Dr. Pranav Khawale,
BNYS, Assistant Professor, Department of
Ozone therapy, National Institute of Naturopathy, Pune.
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ABSTRACT:

The present case study evaluates an Acne Vulgaris patient who visited Nisarg Gram Nature Cure Hospital. Conversations with the patient uncovered that the patient was being treated for Acne vulgaris, and the patient portrayed his capacity to understand the diet modification, Physical activity, lifestyle, mental pressure, and approaches through a natural way related to Acne vulgaris.

There was a significant improvement in quality of life (QOL), perceived Stress, Acne-specific Quality of Life questionnaire score, as well as Sleep quality within 1 week of treatment.

The present case study is an attempt to provide integrative medicine (yoga, Naturopathy, Ozone therapy, Diet modification for the promotion of positive health, and management of Acne vulgaris.

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Keywords: yoga, Naturopathy, Ozone therapy, Diet modification for the promotion of positive health, and management of Acne vulgaris.

INTRODUCTION:

Acne is a chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous unit resulting from androgen-induced increased sebum production, altered keratinisation, inflammation, and bacterial colonisation of hair follicles on the face, neck, chest, and back by *Propionibacterium acnes*(1).

Acne affects almost all people aged 15 to 17 years (2–4) and is moderate to severe in approximately 15–20%. Prevalence estimates are difficult to compare because definitions of acne and acne severity have differed significantly between studies, and because estimates are confounded by the availability and use of acne treatments (5). Surveys of self-reported acne have proven unreliable.16 although perceived as a teenage disease, acne often persists into adulthood (6, 7)

It is considered an adolescent disorder characterised by the formation of open and closed comedones, papules, pustules, nodules, and cysts (8). Accumulation of excess sebum, epithelial cells, and keratin obstructs the pilosebaceous follicle. This obstruction causes the formation of a keratin plug and follicle swelling below the skin surface, resulting in an acne lesion. Colonised bacteria of the skin, such as *Propionibacterium*. Acne may cause a severe kind of infection which leads to scarring and unpleasantness of the face (9).

Acne typically begins in early puberty, characterised by increased facial sebum production, followed by mid-facial comedones (10), and subsequently by inflammatory lesions. Early-onset acne (before the age of 12 years) is usually more than inflammatory.

Fig. 01 -Schematic illustration of the major distinguishing features of the two types of lesions (non-inflammatory, inflammatory).

Pathophysiology

The origin of acne vulgaris is complex and incompletely understood. At least four

pathophysiologic events take place within acne-infected hair follicles: (1) androgen-mediated stimulation of sebaceous gland activity, (2) abnormal keratinisation leading to follicular

plugging (comedo formation), (3) proliferation of the bacterium *Propionibacterium acnes* within the follicle, and (4) inflammation. In addition to these four basic mechanisms, genetic factors (11), Stress (12), and possibly diet may influence the development and severity of acne (13)

CASE PRESENTATION:

Patient comes with complaints of being Prone to acne on the face area since puberty, has undergone allopathic medications (hormonal tablets), and also complains about dryness of skin and hair fall since puberty. Since a 5-year condition is getting worse due to her duty timings and the more intake of outside food habits, as well as a lack of physical activity. Patient is having low self-esteem due to her

skin condition, and she always finds herself at a low confidence level.

Condition diagnosed as acne vulgaris, Constipation, and Xerosis cutis and given treatment for the same. Naturopathy, Yoga therapy, Ozone therapy, and Diet guidelines help patients achieve better results and maintain a healthy lifestyle.

Aim: Reduce acne on the skin and maintain a healthy lifestyle pattern.

Objectives:

- To Regulate GUT health.
- To reduce pigmentation.
- To promote a healthy skin routine
- Improve the quality of sleep.

Fig. 02 -Schematic illustration of the Role of Treatment in Acne vulgaris.

Day wise Treatment Protocol:

	Naturopathy Protocol(14)	Yoga Protocol (15)	Home remedies(16)	Ozone therapy	Diet Protocol(17)
1st day	Neutral water enema Steam bath.	Loosening practices Suryanamskara	Alovera jel application	RI @10mg/250ml to 350ml 10 days (alternative days)	Avoid- Spicy, Oily, Salty Take fresh fruits and vegetables with a Regular diet 3lit/ day water intake
2 nd day	Mud application face Acupuncture face Mud pk abdomen	Kriya -Vaman dhauti Pranayama- Nadi suddhi Bhramari Every day for 06 days.	Neem water face wash		
3rd day	Mud pack to the eye Neutral Immersion Bath Steam bath		Alovera jel application		
4 th day	Acupuncture face Neutral spinal spray SS Steam bath		Neem water face wash		
5 th day	PM head neck mud pk face Steam bath		Alovera jel application		
6 th day	Full mud bath		Neem water face wash		

Table No. 01- Treatment Protocol given to the patient for 6 days.

Personal History:

	Pre
Appetite	More (3-4 times a day)
Sweat	Normal in frequency(during physical activity)
Micturition	Normal in frequency (4-5 times a day) (Night absent)
Diet	Mixed (Non-vegetarian once in 15 days)
Sleep	Sound sleep
Habits	Not such as
Thirst	4-5 glasses per day
Bowel movement	Irregularly regular (Constipation)
Allergies	Nil
Addiction	Nil

Table No. 02- Personal history of the patient

	Pre	Post
Pulse rate	71	69
Respiratory rate	18	18
blood pressure	100/80	110/80
Temperature	Afebrile	Afebrile

Table no: 03- Vital parameters

	Pre	Post
Height	157cm	157cm
Weight	61.1	
Body mass index	24.7	

Table no: 04- Anthropometric measurement

Gravida	-
Para	-
Abortion	-
Living	-
Caesarian	-
Menarche	At the age of 13 years
LMP	30 th March 2025
Cycle	Regular
Menopause	-
HRT	-

Table no: 05- OB/G History

Built	Moderate
Pallor	Absent
Icterus	Absent
Cyanosis	Absent
Clubbing	Absent
Lymphadenopathy	Absent
Oedema	Absent
Skin (appearance)	Dry skin

Table No. 05- General Physical Examination

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION ACCORDING TO NATUROPATHY

Facial Diagnosis/ Encumbrance: Mixed encumbrance.

Tongue Diagnosis: Healthy tongue with typical colouration.

Iris Diagnosis:

<i>Right iris</i>	<i>Left iris</i>
Radi solaris, stress ring, open lesions, closed lesions, scurf ring.	Radi solaris, stress ring, open lesions, closed lesions, scurf ring.

Picture 01- Right Iris and Left Iris Image.

	Pre	Post
Quality of life questionnaire score	68	65
Stress scale score	28	26
Acne-specific Quality of Life questionnaire score	28	101
Pittsburgh Sleep Scale score	7	6

Table No. 06- Pre and Post-Data of Questionnaires

Picture 02: Pre and post-changes in the condition

Diagnosis: Acne vulgaris.

DISCUSSION:

Acne vulgaris is a condition where lifestyle changes, such as reduced physical activity, Stress,

and Irregular bowel movements, contribute as a causative factor and lead to inflammation of the local skin on the face.

Naturopathic Understanding to Prognosis of Disease.

Fig: 03 -Naturopathic Understanding of the Prognosis in Acne Vulgaris

Integrated approach of Therapy which includes Naturopathy, Yoga therapy, Ozone therapy, Diet modification, and home remedies plays a vital role in not only curing but also. Naturopathic treatment focuses on identifying and addressing the root cause, rather than just the symptoms. Naturopathy treatments, such as enemas and healthy food habits, support gut health with probiotics and fibre. Stress increases cortisol, which can stimulate oil production and worsen acne. Yoga practice supports acne treatment through its effects on reducing Stress, balancing hormones, and improving circulation.. Ozone therapy is a less conventional approach and must be administered by a trained professional. It involves using medical-grade ozone (O_3) for its antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties. Kills bacteria (*C. acnes*), reduces inflammation, enhances oxygenation of skin tissues, Stimulates regenerative healing of acne lesions and

scars. Role of Rectal Insufflation in Acne Vulgaris (18): Rectal insufflation (RI) of ozone is an emerging supportive therapy for managing acne vulgaris, a chronic inflammatory skin disorder characterised by comedones, pustules, and nodules. This condition is often associated with factors such as excessive sebum production, colonisation by *Cutibacterium acnes*, hormonal imbalances (particularly elevated androgens), and inflammation. Recent evidence suggests that gut health and systemic inflammation play a significant role in the pathogenesis of acne, a concept commonly referred to as the gut–skin axis.

When oxygen ozone is administered rectally, it is quickly absorbed through the colonic mucosa and enters the systemic circulation, producing a range of therapeutic effects. One of its main actions is on the gut microbiota. Ozone rectal insufflation helps to modulate the intestinal ecosystem by selectively

reducing pathogenic bacteria while promoting the growth of beneficial strains such as *Lactobacillus* and *Bifidobacterium*. This balance of microorganisms enhances the integrity of the gut barrier, preventing the leakage of endotoxins, commonly referred to as "leaky gut." Leaky gut is known to trigger systemic inflammation and immune dysregulation, both of which can contribute to acne flare-ups (19).

Ozone has strong anti-inflammatory properties. It activates the Nrf2 pathway, which enhances the body's natural antioxidant systems, including glutathione, superoxide dismutase, and catalase. This activation reduces oxidative Stress and lowers levels of inflammatory cytokines, such as TNF- α and IL-6, which are known to worsen the severity of acne. Additionally, RI supports hormonal balance by improving liver and intestinal function, both of which are crucial for hormone metabolism and detoxification. By assisting in the clearance of estrogen and modulating androgen metabolism, RI helps reduce acne related to hormonal imbalances. It also helps regulate insulin sensitivity and lowers

levels of insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), both of which can stimulate sebaceous gland activity and keratinocyte proliferation, thereby contributing to the development of acne.

Furthermore, ozone's antimicrobial properties reduce the bacterial load in the gut and lower endotoxemia. This action indirectly decreases the activation of immune responses that can worsen the effects of *Cutibacterium acnes* on the skin. Ozone also enhances tissue oxygenation, including that of the skin, which supports cellular repair and fosters a clearer complexion. By influencing the immune system, ozone helps shift the inflammatory profile from pro-inflammatory Th17 cells to regulatory T-cells, leading to a more balanced immune environment. Overall, rectal insufflation plays a role in acne management by addressing internal factors such as gut dysbiosis, hormonal imbalance, oxidative Stress, and systemic inflammation. It also aids in detoxification and improves tissue oxygenation (20). The application of aloe vera has a Soothing effect on the skin surface and acts as an anti-inflammatory agent.

Fig: 04 -Schematic illustration of the role of sedentary lifestyle in Acne Vulgaris

RESULT:

The patient underwent a 6-day treatment regimen, including naturopathy, Yoga therapy, Home remedies, Ozone therapy, and Diet modification, which had an impact on acne vulgaris, reducing pigmentation and preventing the formation of new pustules and acne. There is marked improvement in stress level with the help of yoga practices, Impact of Digestion and Bowel moments with the help of Dietary changes, Naturopathy treatment as well Vaman Dauti practices every alternative days for a 6 days and Ozone therapy, Parameters like quality of life and sleep quality also shows a improvement, Patient confidence level has been boost up due to reduce skin pigmentation and the reduce acne new formation.

CONCLUSION:

An integrated approach to alternative medicine is effective in treating acne vulgaris.

Consent for Publication:

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient's parent for publication of this case report and any accompanying images

Conflict of Interests:

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests.

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